

**VIEWS OF HISTORY WORD FORMATION IN THE ENGLISH, UZBEK
LANGUAGES**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8051494>

***Annotation.** In this article, the formation of words in English, Uzbek languages, their similarities and scholars analyzes are given, through which the formation of words according to the above groups and the significance of the resulting words in circulation are given. illuminated.*

***Key words:** complexity, lexical system, grammar, word formation, method, linguists*

The study of word development has unquestionably always been linked to a general interest in language. Panini's efforts sparked an investigation into the subject. Panini was born around 520 BC in the Pakistani town of Shalatula. He is credited with founding the Sanskrit language and culture. In his study, he provided a detailed description of Sanskrit word production that was comparable to that of the time. Following Panini, there was little discernible advancement throughout the seventeenth, eighteenth, and nineteenth centuries. Linguists were not interested in this topic, as previously said, hence research was done in the context of other language concerns.

In this regard, the twentieth century saw a shift. The "Handbuch der Englischen Wortbildungslehre" by Herbert Koziol, published in 1937 (a brief survey of prior studies), and the sixth volume of "A Modern English Grammar on Historical Principles" by Otto Jespersen, published in 1942, are two early works from this period that should be mentioned. Jespersen attempted to provide a perspective on grammatical issues from the outside in this work, but his method is still regarded historical. Despite this, none of these works have signaled a significant shift in interest in wordformation; instead, linguists have focused on grammatical issues. Representatives of American structuralism were more interested in morphemes than words, while the transformational stream of linguists were more interested in sentences, which were larger units than words.

The processes of word formation were considered in morphology in the first stage of the theory of word formation in the 1940s-50s of the XX century, while in the second stage of the theory of word formation in the 1960s-80s of the XX century, morphemics and word formation were recognized as a separate level in language construction and as an independent field department that studies this level.

We know that as the world develops, new concepts and new things appear in the social life of every society, in everyday life, as well as in the production, economic, spiritual, cultural and ideological spheres. As a result, there is a need to evaluate these new concepts and things, to express their new facets. Such a need objectively requires new words and names in the language. To meet this communicative need, a language borrows words from other languages or creates new words using its existing internal capabilities. This feature is related to "the law of language economics".

V. Vinogradov's opinion on the role of word formation in linguistics is also important. According to him, while word-formation plays an important role in the science of linguistics, it approaches lexicology - the science of the lexical structure of language, in its place with

grammar - the doctrine of form formation also is interrelated with compound syntax. The number of supporters of this view is growing day by day. This means that word formation is always studied in linguistics along with lexicology, phonetics, and grammar.

Let us discuss some important research and studies on word-formation of the English language. Evidently, H. Marchand, L. Bauer, A. Hatcher, A. I. Smirnitsky, Z. A. Kharitonchik, O. D. Meshkov, and A. N. Ilina are among the linguists who have investigated word formation in English.

In 1960, a major breakthrough occurred in conjunction with the publication of two seminal books that influenced the future of wordformation. R.B.Lees wrote “The Grammar of English Nominalizations” and Hans Marchand wrote “The Categories and Types of Present-Day English Word Formation”.

Linguists' perceptions on word formation changed dramatically with the publication of these two studies. They began to work on this topic, and the following books were published soon after: “An Introduction to Modern English Word Formation” by Valerie Adams in 1973, “English Word-Formation” by Laurie Bauer in 1983, “Wortbildung und Semantik” by Dieter Kastovsky in 1982, “Lexikologija anglijskogo jazyka” by A.I.Smirnitskij in 1956, or “Word Formation in Generative Grammar” by Mark Ar (1976). Milo Dokulil, Josef Filipec, and Ján Horeck, among other Czech and Slovak linguists, contributed to this surge.

The most well-known linguists, Hans Marchand's contribution to the theory of word formation in general and the description of English word formation, in particular, has been undeniably influential, and his handbook “The categories and types of Present-day English word-formation” (1st ed. 1960, 2nd ed. 1969) is still regarded as a seminal work in the field.

According to D. Kastovsky, Hans Marchand’s theoretical framework, which he had developed in the 1940s, had its primary roots in European structuralism, but was also influenced by American structuralism: as a student of Leo Spitzer in the 1930s he had come into contact with European/French structuralism, but during his stay in the U.S. in the late 1940s and 1950s he had become familiar with the basic tenets of American structuralism, whose basically anti-semantic bias he objected to quite vehemently.

This primarily descriptive-structuralist approach to word formation, which characterized the first edition of his handbook, was later modified to some extent by an attempt to incorporate certain insights from generative-transformational grammar, particularly in connection with a critical discussion of Lees' (programmatic book *The grammar of English nominalizations* in Marchand, which eventually found its way into the second edition of his handbook.

Marchand's word-formation theory is synchronic (as opposed to prior approaches, which were all diachronic, cf. Jespersen 1942, Koziol 1937), yet he does address historical issues in his handbook “A synchronic-diachronic approach”.

Furthermore, It Marchand’s handbook “A synchronic-diachronic approach” is focused on the following fundamental principles:

Firstly, a synchronic description has priority; only after a synchronic description has been provided can one look at the history of the patterns characterizing a synchronic system.

Secondly, a synchronic description of **word-formation patterns** has to be based on the notions of motivation/analysability, pattern, and productivity, which involve as additional central notion that of the **syntagma**, a combination of a **determinant** (modifier) and a **determinatum** (head).

Thirdly, a synchronic description of word-formation has to recognize the existence of systematic **morphophonemic alternations**, which have to be treated in terms of their synchronic function, not their historical origin. This might require the distinction between two levels of word-formation, a native and a non-native one, though not in a purely etymological, but in a structural-functional sense.

We grasp derivation on the morphologic basis of another language when we say word-formation on a foreign base of coining. Most learned scientific or technical words in English are morphologically based on Latin or Greek.) Marchand points out that a phonological (phonemic), morpho-phonemic opposition cannot be established solely on the basis of semantic association. For the speaker, the words "dine" and "dinner," "maintain" and "maintenance," and many others are semantically related, but no derivative connection has emerged from such pairs, therefore their opposition has no bearing on word creation.

As a result, we research synchronically those aspects of word-formation that characterize today's English language system, whereas diachronically we look into the history of word formation. The historical system of word-formation does not necessarily correspond to the synchronic type of word-formation.

Additionally, H. Marchand's description of the many types of word production is interesting, as well. He distinguished two major groups:

1) words formed as grammatical syntagmas, (i.e. combinations of full linguistic signs which are characterised by morphological motivation such as do-er, un-do, rain-bow), which includes (Compounding, Suffixation, Prefixation, Derivation by a Zero Morpheme and Back-Derivation,

2) words which are not grammatical syntagmas,(i.e. which are not made up of full linguistic signs) including Expressive Symbolism, Blending, Clipping, Rime and Ablaut Geminatio, Word-Manufacturing.

Here Rime and Ablaut Geminatio are based on the notion of words coming in phonetically varied rhythmic twin forms, such as bibble-babble, shilly-shally, boogie-woogie, claptrap, and so on. Word-Manufacturing is the process of creating artificial new words by joining together more or less arbitrary elements of existing words, such as Pluto ('pipeline under the ocean'), Cominch ('Commander-in-Chief,' and so on.

As we have pointed out, the phenomena of word-building have become a contentious discussion, one of the most serious issues in linguistics that has yet to lose its complexity. Word-building is the process of creating new lexical units using the language's capabilities and supplies. The lexical system of a language is regularly enhanced by calculating the elements that influence lexical meaning change, word development, and the formation of new words. These components, which interact with one another, help to keep language development in one place. Their interdependence is that when newly introduced words are related to word mastering, word mastering plays a significant part in determining the meaning of lexical units.

Word production may appear easy, but it is the most difficult process in all areas except linguistics, as the core of object and subject analysis is immensely diverse, as history has demonstrated. The reason for this is that the laws must be proven directly through linguistic analysis. For these reasons, scholars sometimes include the phenomenon of word formation in morphology, and sometimes in lexicology. In many scientific works, word production is

discussed in the framework of grammar, although in other types of literature, it is discussed as part of lexicology.

The difference between word formation and other branches of linguistics is that this field and its units are closely related to almost all branches of linguistics. Word formation is a complex field that deals with the emergence of new lexical units in a language, their structural features, and classification.

In this part of the dissertation work we try to throw light to the research on the studies of word-formation in the English, Uzbek languages.

When it comes to the Uzbek language, In Uzbek linguistics, the topic of word formation is extensively researched. In linguistics, the phrase "word formation" has two meanings: on the one hand, it refers to the process of word development in a language, and on the other hand, it refers to the study of the linguistics word formation system. The study of the structure and word production of words in a language is known as word formation. These can be used to define the standards of word construction in current Uzbek literary language and to comprehend its characteristics.

A. Gulyamov is one of the scientists who has created excellent research on word formation. In his works, all the basic concepts of word formation have found their deep scientific interpretation on the basis of the best achievements in science and practice, personal observations. Although A. Gulyamov said that the phenomenon of word formation in 1955 was a separate field, the opinion of the Uzbek scholar that "word formation has its own object" was fully recognized in Russian linguistics. Only then did this opinion "revive" Uzbek linguists. Unfortunately, this "revival" also resulted in the emergence of a scientific grammar called Uzbek grammar in 1975, in which Professor A. Gulyamov re-established the "word formation" in practice as a separate branch of linguistics, the Uzbek language system as happened in the late 80s.

There are different views in the literature on word formation and word formation in word categories. Most of the literature emphasizes that word formation is mainly related to independent word groups. "The phenomenon of word formation is unique to independent categories. The composition of nouns, adjectives, verbs and adverbs is always enriched with new constructions". A similar view can be found in K. Sapayev's textbook "Modern Uzbek language".

In the following years, new views on word formation were put forward, in particular, in A. Hodzhiev's monograph Theoretical problems of morphology, morphemics and word formation of the Uzbek language. Speaking about the study of word formation in Uzbek, the linguist said that the study of each system of language begins with the definition of the language unit that forms this system, but this is the main, important in the study of the system of word formation in Uzbek. and that a certain fact has not been taken into account, that is, the question of whether the Uzbek language has a word-formation system and its linguistic unity has been raised, and no definite opinion has been expressed on it.

In this monograph, A. Hodjiyev analyzes the existing views on word formation, word structure, the possibility of word formation in Uzbek linguistics.

In the following years, new objections have been put forward in Uzbek linguistics on the subject of word formation. Most of the literature on linguistics gives the following methods of word formation in Uzbek. "There are different means of word formation in Uzbek language, and

its types are as follows: 1) phonetic method; 2) semantic method; 3) affixation (morphological); 4) composition (syntactic) method and 5) abbreviation.

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